

SHORT NOTES

Beckmann Rearrangement and Semmler-Wolff Aromatisation of 7-Methoxy-1-tetralone Oxime

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It has been reported that 1-tetralone oxime (I:R=H)¹ and its 2,2-disubstituted derivatives² undergo Beckmann rearrangement with PPA at 125-30° for 10 minutes to 5,6-benzocaprolactam (II: R=H) and its 2,2-disubstituted products. Under the same experimental condition, which is a general procedure³, we found that the rearrangement of 7-methoxy-1-tetralone oxime (I:R=OMe) did not occur and the starting material was recovered unchanged. At a higher temperature, 170°, a tarry product was obtained. But the reaction mixture, on being kept at 125-30° for 2 hours, afforded a single lactam in 70% yield, the structure of which was unequivocally established as (II:R=OMe) by the method of Conley and Franier⁴. It was hydrolysed with dilute sulphuric acid to the amine hydrogen sulphate which was directly diazotised; treatment of the resulting diazonium salt with alkaline β -naphthol furnished a dark red insoluble dye. Since (II:R=OMe) and not (III:R=OMe) would react in the coupling reaction, the position of the amino group, and consequently the structure of the lactam, was substantiated. Thus the lactam formed is the result of phenyl migration, as is expected from the normal course of rearrangement⁵.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

That the cyclohexenone oximes undergo aromatisation to the corresponding anilines by acidic reagents was first reported by Semmler³, and later described by Wolff⁴ to be a general reaction^{5,6}. Bauer and Hewitson⁷ recently reported interesting observation on the Semmler-Wolff aromatisation and Beckmann rearrangement of 2-[β -(2- and 4-pyridyl)ethyl]-1-tetralone oximes. Treatment of the oximes with acetic anhydride in

1. Horning *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 5153.

2. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 3844.

3. *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 3352.

4. *Annalen*, 1892, 322, 351.

5. "Organic Reactions", Vol. XI, Wiley, 1960, p. 30.

6. Vorozhtsov and Kopitug, *J. Gen. Chem., U.S.S.R.* (Eng. Transl.), 1959, 1997.

7. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 3982.

acetic acid and hydrogen chloride afforded a mixture of 2- $[\beta$ -(2- and 4-pyridyl)ethyl]-1-naphthylamines and 2,3-benzocaprolactams of type (III). They conclude that the latter arise during a Beckmann transformation of the oximes which involves *alkyl* migration since in acidic medium the Beckmann rearrangement must be considered as a possible competing reaction. But, in the conventional Beckmann transformation with PPA, *aryl* migration occurred in these oximes and 5,6-benzocaprolactams of type (II) were formed.

In view of the above findings, we visualised that 7-methoxy-1-tetralone oxime (I: R=OMe) during the Semmler-Wolf rearrangement would give rise to the corresponding naphthylamine (IV) along with the 2,3-benzocaprolactam (III:R=OMe). The latter might arise due to alkyl migration if a competing Beckmann rearrangement were possible under the acidic conditions. This was not, however, realised as we were unable to isolate any lactams: only 7-methoxy-1-naphthylamine (IV) was obtained in 50% yield. Nevertheless, this is in keeping with the observation of Vorozhtsov and Kopitug⁸ who did not obtain any lactam during the Semmler-Wolf aromatisation of 1-tetralone oxime under similar conditions.

7-Methoxy-1-tetralone Oxime.—7-Methoxy-1-tetralone was prepared according to the method of Rao and Dev⁹. It was purified by distillation *in vacuo*; the distillate, b.p. 114-15°/0.8 mm, solidified to large crystalline plates, m.p. 62° (lit.⁹ m.p. 61-62.5°).

The oxime was obtained by modifying the method for oximation prescribed by Feiser¹⁰. A mixture of the tetralone (7.4 g.), sodium acetate (6 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3.06 g.) in ethanol (32 ml), and water (13 ml) was refluxed for 2 hours on a steam bath. After distilling most of the ethanol, the reaction mixture was poured on ice water: on keeping and vigorous stirring, a crystalline solid separated which was filtered, washed with water, and dried in an exiccator; yield 7.4 g., m.p. 86-87° (lit.¹¹ m.p. 87°). This was used for the next step without further purification.

The method¹² for oximation, using hydroxylamine hydrochloride in ethanol-pyridine, provided a gummy product which could not be induced to crystallise.

Beckmann Rearrangement with PPA.—A mixture of 7-methoxy-1-tetralone oxime (2 g.) and PPA, prepared from P₂O₅ (15 g.) and phosphoric acid (9 ml, *d* 1.87), was heated to and maintained at 120-25° for 2 hours. The solution was cooled, diluted with ice-water (150 ml), and extracted with chloroform (3 × 25 ml); the extract was washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the solvent left a solid residue (1.4 g.), m.p. 129-30°. It was purified by recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) when the 5,6-benzocaprolactam (II; R=OMe) was obtained as irregular plates, m.p. 131-32°. (Found: C, 68.8; H, 7.1; N, 7.5. C₁₁H₁₃O₂N requires C, 69.1; H, 6.8; N, 7.3%).

Hydrolysis, Diazotisation, and β -Naphthol Coupling.—Following the prescribed method¹, a mixture of the above lactam (0.2 g.) and H₂SO₄ (30%, 10 ml) was refluxed for

8. This Journal, 1957, 34, 255.

9. Beckmann and Horton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 69, 58.

10. "Experiments in Organic Chemistry", Heath & Co., 3rd ed., p. 103.

11. Davlen *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 191.

12. Beckmann and Barton, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1939, 3, 300.

4 hours, cooled, and diluted with water (20 ml). The solution (3 ml) was chilled in an ice bath and treated with the calculated amount of sodium nitrite in water (25 ml). On adding β -naphthol (1 g.) in aqueous NaOH (10%, 10 ml.), a dark red, insoluble dye was obtained.

Semmler-Wolff Aromatisation with Hydrogen Chloride and Acetic Anhydride in Acetic Acid.—Adopting the reported procedure⁷, a mixture of the oxime (5.4 g.), acetic anhydride (3.75 ml), and glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was heated on a water bath for 10 mins. Dry hydrogen chloride was then passed through the solution at 100° for 50 mins, when a deep red solution was obtained. On being cooled to 0°, grey-coloured crystals of the amine hydrochloride separated; concentration of the mother liquor furnished a second crop of the crystals. These were combined, covered with ether, and treated with excess aqueous ammonia. The liberated amine was extracted with ether several times; the ether extract was washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the solvent furnished the colorless free base, 7-methoxy-1-naphthylamine (IV) which was crystallised from dilute methanol, m.p. 78° (lit⁹. m.p. 79-80°), yield 2.7 g. (50%).

The acetamido derivative was prepared from the amine and acetic anhydride in the usual way and was crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 159-60° (lit⁹. m.p. 160-61°).

The mother liquor from the reaction mixture (after the amine hydrochloride had been filtered) was worked up according to the direction given in the literature⁷. No identifiable product could be isolated; only an intractable material was obtained.